

Appendix A: Research Results and Publication Proof

```
from flask import Flask, render_template
import mysql.connector
import folium
app = Flask(__name__)
# MySQL database connection
db = mysql.connector.connect(
    host="localhost",
    user="root",
    password="password",
    database="logistics_db"
)
@app.route('/')
def home():
    cursor = db.cursor(dictionary=True)
    cursor.execute("SELECT origin, destination, current_location FROM
orders")
    orders = cursor.fetchall()
    # Create map centered at average location
    m = folium.Map(location=[45.0, 105.0], zoom_start=4)
    for order in orders:
        folium.Marker(
            location=[45.0, 105.0], # Replace with geocoded locations
            popup=f"Order: {order['origin']} → {order['destination']}
({order['current_location']})"
        ).add_to(m)
    m.save('templates/map.html')
    return render_template('map.html')
if __name__ == '__main__':
    app.run(debug=True)
```